

A STUDY ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF PHARMACEUTICAL

(JANANI A*)

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

- ❖ Indian pharmaceutical history began from Gupta period which was existed from approximately 320 to 550 CE. The Indian pharmaceutical industry is the world's second largest industry by volume and is likely to lead the manufacturing sector of India. The first pharmaceutical company is Bengal Chemicals and Pharmaceutical Works establish
- ❖ In 1903 at Calcutta, which still exists today as one of the fifth government owned drug manufacturers. Since then there is no looking back and today, India has become one of the leading pharmaceutical products manufacturing nation. Even without strong patent protection, the Indian pharmaceutical industry matured during 1980s. Companies also started to produce products better tailored for their markets than typical MNCs products.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The following are the specific objectives of the study:-

- ❖ To review the growth of selected Pharmaceutical Companies in India.
- ❖ To analyze the factors determining the profitability, liquidity and solvency of selected Pharmaceutical Companies in India.
- ❖ To analyze the influencing relationship of profitability, liquidity and solvency on the overall performance of selected Pharmaceutical Companies in India.
- ❖ To confer findings and conclusion of this study.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The present study aims at assessing the profitability, liquidity and solvency position of Pharmaceutical Companies in India. The study could help the company as well as the investors to understand its financial efficiency. It aims to help the management to find out its financial problems at present and the specific areas in the business, which might need some effort for more effective and efficient utilization of its resources.

Ratio analysis

- ❖ Ratio analysis is widely used tool of financial analysis. Ratios are relationships expressed in mathematical terms between figures which are connected with each in

some manner. It is defined as the systematic use of ratios to interpret the financial statements so that the strengths and weaknesses of a firm as well as its historical performance and current financial condition can be determined.

Liquidity ratio

Liquidity is the ability of company meets its short-term obligations when they fall due. As company should have enough cash and the current assets, which can be converted into cash so that it can pay its suppliers and lenders on time.

The following ratios are calculated:

- ❖ Current ratio
- ❖ Cash ratio

Current ratio

Current ratio is a widely used indicator of company's ability to pay its debts in the short-term. It is the relationships between current assets and current liabilities. Current assets are those assets which can be easily converted into cash within a short period of time or with in an operating cycle generally one year. Current liabilities are those which are payable with in a short period of time generally one year.

$$\text{Current ratio} = \frac{\text{Current assets}}{\text{Current liabilities}}$$

Cash ratio

Cash ratio means the availability to meet out the current liabilities. This ratio is also named as "Absolute Liquid Ratio". It is the Relationship between the Absolute liquid assets include cash in hand, cash at bank and marketable securities or temporary investments.

$$\text{Cash ratio} = \frac{\text{Cash}}{\text{Current liabilities}}$$

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Prasanna Chandra (1975) according to his study stated that a significant relationship existed between the share price and the variables like return, risk, growth size, leverage, etc. Thus, leverage or the debt-equity mix in the capital structure is also one of the factors affecting the value of a share of a firm.

Bhatt (1980) in his paper concludes that the leverage ratio is very much influenced by business risks measured in term of variability in earnings, profitability, debt service capacity, and dividend payout ratio.

CHAPTER III

OVER VIEW

MARKET CAPITALIZATION

The Indian pharmaceutical industry consists of more than 20,000 registered units which are highly fragmented. It has been expanding in a tremendous manner in the last two decades and includes 250 Pharmaceutical Companies which control 70% of the market.

SIZE OF THE INDUSTRY

The Indian pharma industry has around 70% of the country's demand for bulk drugs, drug intermediates, pharmaceutical formulations, chemicals, tablets, capsules, orals and injectables. 250 large units and about 8000 small scale units, form the core of the pharmaceutical industry in India. The units produced have the complete range of medicines which are ready for consumption by patients.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The study focuses on the performance of profitability, liquidity and solvency of Pharmaceutical Companies in India, which may be interesting not only to those manufacturing Pharmaceutical or related products but also to others to see the process of change within the industry. This study will be useful to the management from the point of decision-making purpose, to identify the strength, weak areas of the company and finally helps to maximize the fundamental value of the company. The study has the academic and practical significance.

RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

Both the Indian central and state governments have recognised R&D as an important driver in the growth of their pharmaceutical businesses and conferred tax deductions for expenses related to research and development. They have granted other concessions as well, such as reduced interest rates for export financing and a cut in the number of drugs under price control. Government support is not the only thing in Indian pharma's favor, though companies also have access to a highly-developed IT industry that can partner with them in new molecule discovery.

OPPORTUNITIES OF INDIAN PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRY

Multinational pharmaceutical companies are looking towards Pharmerging countries due to the change in the global pharmaceutical market and low growth in developed market like the US, Japan, and EU. The Indian pharmaceutical sector offers a wide range of opportunities for the pharmaceutical companies to establish their units and market their products in India. Supportive regulatory framework and availability of large number of scientists and professionals is an added advantage for the pharmaceutical companies in India. The huge

investment in infrastructure and larger domestic market made in India is one of the favorite destinations for pharmaceutical companies. Indian Pharmaceutical sector is looking towards promising future because of Low cost of production and developed R&D infrastructure.

FUTURE OF THE INDUSTRY

- ▶ Indian pharmaceutical sector accounts for about 2.4 per cent of the global pharmaceutical industry in value terms and 10 per cent in volume terms and is expected to expand at a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 15.92 per cent to US\$ 55 billion by 2020 from US\$ 20 billion in 2015. By 2016, India is expected to be the third-largest global generic Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient (API) merchant market. The country accounts for the second largest number of Abbreviated New Drug Applications (ANDAs) and is the world's leader in Drug Master Files (DMFs) applications with the US.
- ▶ Indian drugs are exported to more than 200 countries in the world, with the US as the key market. Generic drugs account for 20 per cent of global exports in terms of volume, making the country the largest provider of generic medicines globally and are expected to expand even further in the coming years. The Government of India plans to set up a US\$ 640 million venture capital fund to boost drug discovery and strengthen the pharmaceutical infrastructure. The 'Pharma Vision 2020' by the Government's Department of Pharmaceuticals aims to make India a major hub for end-to-end drug discovery.

CHAPTER IV
ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

GROSS PROFIT RATIO

Year	Gross Profit	Net Sales	Gross Profit Ratio
2021-2020	204.51	1161.29	17.61
2020-2019	288.90	1422.33	20.31
2019-2018	419.64	1652.45	25.39
2018-2017	535.80	1953.40	27.42
2017-2016	625.14	2327.90	26.85
2016-2015	582.12	2708.40	21.49
2015-2014	527.64	3137.56	16.81
2014-2013	971.05	3951.04	24.57
2013-2012	994.59	4548.23	21.86
2012-2011	1074.31	5300.26	20.26

INTERPRETATION

The table dealt with the gross profit ratio from the year 2020-2011. In the year 2013-2012 it deceased to (21.86) again in 2012-2011 it decreased to 20.26 Hence, the company has not earned profit, the company has to take necessary steps to increase its sales or reduce it cost (expenses).

DEBT RATIO

YEAR	Total Debt	Net Asset	Debt Ratio
2021-2020	203.29	160.10	1.26
2020-2019	158.28	13.52	11.70
2019-2018	189.41	63.73	2.97
2018-2017	123.46	108.03	1.14
2017-2016	128.94	189.64	0.67
2016-2015	70.86	328.20	0.21
2015-2014	67.22	456.87	0.14
2014-2013	0.00	562.83	0
2013-2012	0.00	794.82	0
2012-2011	0.00	743.13	0

INTERPRETATION

The debt ratio for the year 2020-2011 is 16.83. This position was not good to conduct business in future. Hence, the company has to take necessary step to avoid borrowing loan from bank

or others. Huge debts carries huge amount of interest, it affects the profitability of the concern

CHAPTER V

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSIONS

FINDINGS

For the period 2020-2011, the current ratio witnessed a fall due to low sundry debtors and cash and bank balances but very high current liabilities. The average rate maintained by the firm was 2.46.

- ❑ The debt ratio for the year 2020-2011 is 16.83. This position was not good to conduct business in future.
- ❑ The table dealt with the gross profit ratio from the year 2010-2019. Profitability declined in the years 2014-2013, 2013-2012, 2012-2011.

CONCLUSIONS

Paramedicines needs to monitor its financial performance continuously and takes financial decisions for competing with global economic scenario and maintain its sustainable position. The success of every business undertaking depends on share of their investments in Research and Development, innovation and other developmental activities. In view of globalization, the sustainable growth is assured only if the companies are competitive by developing and exploiting new technologies. Finance being the nerve center of any organization, its management is crucial to survive, grow and also to maximize wealth. Decisions by the financial managers in turn lead to maximizing profitability, solvency and the shareholders' wealth.